

FORMATION OF A SYSTEM OF ATTITUDE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS TO LEARNING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The article describes in detail that there are a number of problems that the system of psychological service should solve and eliminate today in the organization and management of the educational activities of schoolchildren through observations on the psychological analysis of the educational process of adolescent schoolchildren.*

Key words: *motivation, active-positive, positive, indifferent, cognitive, emotional-volitional, evaluative component, adequate assessment.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ОТНОШЕНИЯ ПОДРОСТКОВ К УЧЕБНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В статье подробно описано, что существует ряд проблем, которые должна решить и устранить сегодня система психологической службы в организации и управлении воспитательной деятельностью школьников посредством наблюдений, посвященных психологическому анализу воспитательного процесса школьников-подростков.*

Ключевые слова: *мотивация, активно-положительная, положительная, индифферентная, познавательная, эмоционально-волевая, оценочный компонент, адекватная оценка.*

Speaking about the theoretical and methodological foundations of psychological services, it is necessary to pay special attention to studies showing the promise of an approach based on a system of attitude towards a person, who is considered as an object and subject of psychological services. The psychological service process, based on the same areas of research, sets itself the task of analyzing the relationships of a person in the process of his activities and determining appropriate measures on this basis. Because without studying and analyzing the social level of relationships that develop in relation to oneself, others (interpersonal) and activities that inevitably manifest themselves and develop in the process of psychological services, it is impossible to independently determine the volume of conflict situations associated with the establishment of psychological protection from unpleasant sensations. cooperation with other people, failures in activities. The main factor in the conscious direction of a student towards educational activities is the internal capabilities, interests, talents and needs of the individual.

From this point of view, it is important to study the internal position (motivation) of the subject (student) and the aspect of proportionality to the external environment influencing him in the organization of the educational process. After all, although the student is the object of the process of orientation towards educational activity, he is the subject of the process of self-awareness and conscious attitude. In addition, the analysis of some theoretical and empirical data in the modern scientific press confirms that the student's personality participates in the process of educational activity both as an object and as subject. The center of his participation is the unique socio-psychological features of the formation of a system of relational motivation in the full sense,

theoretically and empirically analyze the scope of these features, and pay serious attention to the issue of developing appropriate socio-psychological recommendations. On this basis is the main goal of psychological services.

In this regard, special emphasis can be placed on the scale and progress of psychological research conducted today by scientists in Uzbekistan. Of course, since the issue of educational activity is a complex process, many of its aspects are revealed through research. It can be said that many psychologists, educators, philosophers, sociologists and people from other fields have done commendable work in this regard. However, despite this, one cannot help but notice the growing need for more detailed studies of the formation of a system of attitude towards educational activity, the formation of its unique socio-psychological hierarchy and motivation, compatible with our modern achievements. Because without a deep study or analysis of the possibilities of real internal (positive) motivation in the student's attitude to the educational process, it is impossible to determine the overall development of the individual and the directions of education that are compatible with social goals.

Conducting theoretical and scientific research aimed at substantiating the concept of relational motivation remains very relevant. In addition, we believe that analysis of this problem can shed light on theoretical concepts related to motivational attitudes towards learning activities. After all, the educational process and attitude towards it are not separate and isolated things, but also represent a socio-psychological process that complements each other and is directed towards a single goal.

Due to the lack of practical manuals on the methodology for studying a student's attitude towards educational activities, today some difficulties arise in the issue of correctly assessing the internal motivation of students in relation to educational activities. To overcome these difficulties, it is necessary to pay attention to the task of developing criteria and a method for studying the system of attitudes towards educational activities.

It is necessary to determine aspects that allow one to accept the attitude towards activity as an important criterion for the effectiveness of setting the motivation for activity and the psychology of activity, a theoretical and scientific analysis of its social significance, opinions on the conclusions. Because the definition of activity (i.e. activity is the internal (mental) and external (physical) activity of a person, controlled by a conscious goal) itself represents a set of human relationships at one level or another. So, accordingly, we can conditionally distinguish three levels of attitude towards activity (active-positive, positive, indifferent).

The purpose of dividing the relational system into these types is a deeper understanding and interpretation of certain socio-psychological aspects that express social activity in the form of attitudes.

In addition, the following direction was chosen, serving the formation of motivation for attitude towards educational activities, and these directions were included in the general goal of the study: in the first direction - to study the motivation of attitude towards school, in - The second direction - to study the levels of formation of educational components of "learning", and in the third direction it is necessary to select a set of methods aimed at studying the motivation of attitude towards educational activities by studying the orientation of the individual and apply this in practice.

The average general, comparatively typical coefficient of motivation of an “actively positive”, “positive”, “indifferent” attitude towards the process of choosing educational activities is formed in the activities of students on the scale of the system of attitudes corresponding to the character. A number of indicators are introduced for adolescent students, which creates the opportunity to analyze socio-psychological criteria suitable for the purpose of the study.

Based on the scientific observations carried out, we considered it necessary to determine the following general and practical tasks:

1. Study of attitude motivation and its specific dynamic features as a socio-psychological problem characteristic of teenage students. Unlike other interpretations of the concept of attitude motivation, we considered it necessary to pay serious attention to considerations associated with the empirical assessment of the dynamics of indicators of attitude motivation.

2. Development of a method of relational motivation and its socio-psychological research. In this case, the question is raised about the creation of a methodological complex that serves to determine indicators of attitude motivation. Because it is impossible to draw appropriate scientific and practical conclusions without identifying methods based on certain fundamental information in the scientific press. To accomplish this task, it is necessary to choose methods that complement each other and are logically connected.

3. Identification of socio-psychological factors that directly influence the motivation of relationships. By posing this question, it will be possible to evaluate the system of factors associated with the formation of direct relationship motivation.

4. Emphasis on the need to assess indicators of attitude motivation and develop appropriate recommendations based on the obtained empirical data in relation to teenage students. When choosing research methods, it is necessary to select criteria developed and used in practice by representatives of advanced psychology to study the system of attitudes based on certain socio-psychological requirements, and to use them correctly.

As we already mentioned above, the following direction was chosen, serving to form a motivational attitude towards learning activities, and a set of clearly oriented methods in these directions was developed. In particular, in the first direction - methods for studying the motivation of general attitudes towards school and educational activities, in the second direction - methods for studying attitude motivation based on the components of educational activities, in the third direction.

by studying the orientation of the individual by methods of studying the motivation of attitude towards educational activities; in the fourth direction, it is advisable to highlight a set of methods aimed at studying the motivation of attitudes towards educational activities through values.

The set of methods included in the first direction is called “motivation of attitude towards school.” Because the readiness of each student to complete educational tasks is seen primarily on the basis of his positive or indifferent attitude towards the educational process at school. Because it is possible to develop a set of measures aimed at increasing educational activity with each student through assessing the system of general attitudes towards school education for an individual student.

From this point of view, the first set of methods includes the methodology “Assessing the motivation of attitude towards school”, developed and recommended by N.G. Luskanova (source: Luskanova N.G. Methods for studying children with learning difficulties. - M., 1993; 2). Psychodiagnostic methods for studying personality. Editor-in-Chief Ratanova T.A., Moscow Psychological and Social Institute: Flint, 1998-264 p. - we took as a basis for determining the level of emotional relationships. Of course, in addition to this technique, the results of individual interviews, answers to questionnaires, special observations and content analysis can also be used.

Procedure for using the method. The method consists of 10 situational survey questions, the answer to each question serves to determine the levels of attitude motivation in a certain sense. Therefore, first, questionnaire questions are prepared and distributed to respondents. In each of the distributed questions of the questionnaire, there are 3 answer options, and the respondent is asked to choose the one that is closest to him. To find out the correctness of the answers to the questionnaire, the experimenter once again repeats the questions and their content, and also records the results of an individual interview with each respondent within the chosen direction of the answer. When everything is finished, the experimenter collects the completed questionnaires and begins processing the data.

First of all, it should be said that this set of methods serves to determine the degree of inclusion of educational components in the student's activities. Because any activity is based on certain factors. In our opinion, the participation of educational components (cognitive, emotional-volitional, evaluative) is important in the motivation of educational activity or attitude towards the manifestation of educational activity. That is, we can talk about educational activities, forming an educational component at the appropriate level. In addition, in order for a student to be an active participant in the process of completing any educational task, his knowledge, emotional and volitional qualities, and targeted efforts to adequately assess and develop his motivation must first be formed. Otherwise, the activity in it is assessed as a simple action. Taking this into account, it is necessary to determine the levels of formation of educational components that underlie the attitude motivation that serves to demonstrate educational activity in teenage schoolchildren.

It is necessary to highlight educational components that serve to ensure an active and positive attitude towards learning activities among students. Because depending on the amount of each component at a particular level, one can make appropriate judgments about the indicators of attitude motivation (high, medium, low) in relation to educational activities.

In particular, the participation of the cognitive component in most cases is determined by the presence in the student's activities of interests based on the acquisition of relevant knowledge, and the manifestation of the desire to complete each educational task through deeper perception and thinking.

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